

DIGITAL PEDAGOGY AND ITS IMPORTANCE IN EDUCATION.

Bainiyazov Daniyar

Nukus State Pedagogical Institute named after Ajinyaz
first-year doctoral student in 13.00.01 - Theory of Pedagogy. The history of
pedagogical teachings.

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Anatation. The article highlights the significance and possibilities of digital pedagogy in education, as well as methods for using digital technologies in education.

Key words. Digital pedagogy, digital technologies.

In the 21st century, knowledge will be developed not only through books, but also through the internet and modern technologies. In today's education system, if a teacher cannot provide an education that meets the needs and desires of students, such an education system is considered outdated. Modern youth do not like obsolete education, if they are taught using modern technologies, it will be easier to master any subject, and the education system will be much more developed. Global education systems need to change rapidly to accommodate 21st-century learners to modern technologies.

In the digital world, information and communication technologies, interacting, make a significant contribution to the development of the education system. The involvement of these technologies allows for the use of online assignments, video lessons, online tests, computer and mobile applications in various fields. It is advisable to define pedagogical tasks through the use of these technologies.

Digital Pedagogy Lab va Hybrid Pedagogy jurnalining hammuassisi J. Strommel raqamli pedagogika raqamli vositalarni fetishizatsiya qilmaydigan pedagogikaga yo'naltirilganligini alohida ta'kidlaydi [1]. If the first rule implies that the goal of using digital technologies in pedagogical activity is not to replace existing forms of learning, but to seek new forms that can increase the effectiveness of the teacher and his students, then the second rule reminds us of the importance of the role of using digital technologies in the teacher and his students.

Pedagogy has never stood still, and it is natural that new formats appear in it. In the modern era, firstly, you will observe that the conditions for digital pedagogy have been shaped over centuries, some of them have come to secondary importance due to new discoveries in psychology and pedagogy, changes in the educational paradigm and changes in public life, and some have remained relevant and laid the foundation for these innovations.

Technological changes are constantly changing the priorities that need to be studied. For example, new literacy, such as video, animation, and creating websites and apps, is very important.

Remembering knowledge is no longer important because open educational resources can find all kinds of information on the Internet. Priority is given to how to enhance the ability to find information, understand information when necessary, and evaluate the information found. At the same time, education for adolescents and adults is the responsibility of everyone:

1. Content is more focused on general skills, such as solving problems and interacting with multiple media outlets, finding resources, and learning how to use these resources;
2. Pedagogy develops in the direction of interdependence.
3. Interaction includes technologies such as video lessons, online games, or interaction with other people through computer networks;
4. Assessment is conducted after mastering a computer-based learning environment to measure the success of students in achieving their educational goals.
5. Educational institutions will now include various places, such as houses, offices and educational centers, where access to educational materials is available not only in educational institutions, but also through the Internet;
6. Peer culture may be weakened, and students may have difficulty completing homework and independent assignments with their parents, peers, or even be isolated from others on a computer network;
7. Changing the forms of relationships in the educational process. [2]

Some of the above-mentioned changes in the field of education are relevant today for many people in different parts of the world. Changes in the paradigm of education management are becoming the focus of attention for various stakeholders. Traditional pedagogy should be structured in accordance with the dynamics that arise. Education, considered correct, is a digital world alongside online education and character education.

Digital pedagogy as an educational solution for the digital age The struggle for technology and pedagogy demonstrates a boundless striving for universal education and teaching methods that best fit all types of content, students, and learning goals. This is due to the fact that each new interactive media is a leader in solving educational problems in the digital environment.

New digital technologies always create a creative explosion of ideas in teaching and learning. To find the best approach, it is first necessary to understand the

needs of students and teachers. Ideally, teachers decide to integrate technology into their education based on an internal desire to improve learning outcomes and student experience.

Digital technologies can facilitate personalized learning, for example, students can decide to choose a specific educational path. They can enable collaborative learning, where the building of knowledge is the result of interaction and negotiation. Digital technologies can also be used by teachers to collect data supporting the analytical learning process.

The International Society for Educational Technologies (ISTE) identifies seven skills that students need to learn effectively to live effectively in a globally increasingly digital world, namely:

1. Digital citizens who recognize the rights, obligations, and opportunities to live, learn, and work in an interconnected digital world for educational purposes, and who act with safe, ethical, and exemplary paths;
2. Digital citizens who accept the rights, obligations, and opportunities to live, learn, and work in an interconnected digital world for educational purposes.
3. Problem solving through the creation of new, useful, or imaginary solutions the design process involves the use of various technologies for detection and resolution used innovative designers;
4. Technological methods for developing and testing solutions to understand and solve problems using the power of calculator thinkers;
5. Specifically communicate and creatively express themselves for various purposes, using appropriate platforms, tools, methods, formats, and digital media for their purposes creative communicators;
6. Global which uses digital tools to broaden their horizons and enrich learning by collaborating with others and working effectively in local and global communities partners. [2]

Digital pedagogy in the integration of technology in education can be based on the philosophy of. Digital pedagogy digital technology involvement and reflection in teaching and learning activities through is defined as. Features of digital pedagogy are as follows:

- Combining theory and practice, creation and thinking;
- Developing creativity, play, and problem-solving;
- Promotion of participation, cooperation and public engagement;
- Enhance critical understanding of the digital environment.

Digital pedagogy is the joint development of knowledge. Digital pedagogy is less meaningful than problem-solving including learning planning. This approach provides knowledge may present as a problem rather than an improvement. Therefore, he demonstrates a high level of thinking ability and students can deepen their understanding of the content they transition to a conceptual understanding.

In conclusion, it can be said that digital pedagogy is the pedagogy of the future, and if education is digitized from now on, there will be more scientific and educated young people.

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